

REUSE OF RECYCLED CARBON FIBERS FOR REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) are being employed to a growing extent across various industrial sectors. As the number of components and semi-finished products continues to rise, there is a corresponding need for an increased production of carbon fibers. Consequently, this also results in a higher volume of production waste and end-of-life components. Currently, the recycling of these end-of-life components is limited, hindering the establishment of an optimal closed material cycle for carbon fibers. This article introduces the collaborative project "Change through Innovation in the Region (WIR!)" and outlines its objectives.

KEYWORDS

Carbon fibers; recycling; carbon reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

Motivation

Fiber-reinforced composites or plastics made from carbon fibers (CFRP) are finding more and more applications in all areas of life, both in Germany and around the world. Thanks to their high performance, low weight and resistance (for example chemical resistance and corrosion resistance) to external influences, they make a significant contribution to the conservation of resources.

Applications range from ultra-lightweight spectacle frames, household and leisure equipment to wind energy, automotive, marine, aerospace and construction, including semi-finished products such as reinforcements. As a result, annual demand for carbon fibers has increased from 33,000 tonnes in 2010 to over 107,000 tonnes in 2022 (Michael Sauer, 2022).

Waste from composite fiber materials is not only generated at the end of their life, but also during the production of fibers and yarns (Figure 1), as well as during the production of semi-finished products and the composite materials themselves. Given the increasing consumption of resources and energy, as well as the growing CO₂ emissions associated with the production of new fibers, the creation of a circular value chain is a societal challenge. One of the most important aspects of this challenge is the recycling of fiber-containing waste with the goal to get recycled fibers back into the material cycle. This requires the development of technical and organisational processes for the material recovery of fiber fractions, similar to those that exist for metallic materials such as ferrous and non-ferrous metals. It is also necessary to create marketable products from recycled fibers.

Figure 1: Carbon fibers for the production of fiber composites; © C³ Association

At present, there are no comprehensive technical and organisational processes for the extensive material recovery of fiber fractions, similar to those for metallic materials. There is also a lack of marketable products made from recycled fibers, which represents both a risk and an opportunity. The industries located in the "Elbtal Sachsen" region, including technical textiles, lightweight construction and the construction sector with its carbon concrete applications, can only sustain and grow if they address the issue of fiber composite recycling in a timely manner. The project "WIR! recyceln Fasern" (WE! recycle fibers) provides the decisive impetus to utilise the existing knowledge of material recycling and to facilitate the transition from a linear waste management system to a circular economy, with the aim of becoming a global leader in this field.

Research objective

The overarching objectives are to significantly increase the regional innovation capacity and create prospects for further growth and employment through the expansion of the recycling economy and the resource management of fiber composite materials. The innovation of recyclable fiber composites is the cornerstone for the sustainable structural change of the region "Elbtal Sachsen". As a driver of change, the project "WIR!" will initiate this crucial transformation by further developing the existing regional strengths. The numerous prerequisites for this transformation are to be created. With the active participation of various institutions, the focus is not only on material optimisation, collection and consolidation of waste flows, separation and processing of different types of waste, and the development of new products and training concepts, but also on promoting the identification of the "Elbtal Sachsen" region with this future-oriented topic. The five subgoals of the "WIR!" project are as follows:

1. By the end of 2021, all institutions located in the "Elbtal Sachsen" region that are associated with the value chain of fiber composite materials will be interconnected
2. By the end of 2023, initial concrete value chains for fiber composite materials will be planned.
3. By the end of 2025, the first specific value chains for fiber composite materials will be established in the "Elbtal Sachsen" region.
4. Expansion of the value chains for fiber composite materials both within and outside the "Elbtal Sachsen" region.
5. Creation of foundations for further research and development activities in the field of fiber composite materials.

In the context of structural change, the alliance is creating a new impetus for regional development in the economic, scientific, political and social spheres, particularly through innovative applications for the sustainable use of recycled carbon and glass fibers. In the short term, the construction industry, with its use of carbon concrete, represents a specific application area where the requirements for fiber composite products in terms of mechanical properties and aesthetic appearance are more flexible than

in other industries. In the medium term, further applications in lightweight construction, mechanical engineering and the automotive industry will expand the product portfolio, initially by combining recycled and virgin fibers for structural components, and later by using only recycled fibers. In the long term, it is expected that recycled carbon and glass fibers will have a comparable processability and quality to primary fibers, enabling applications in the aerospace industry.

WIR-alliance

The region "Elbtal Sachsen" extends along the river Elbe and its surrounding catchment areas. It borders Poland to the east, the Czech Republic to the south, overlaps the northern border of Brandenburg and shares borders with Saxony-Anhalt and Thuringia to the west. The extent of the 'Elbtal Sachsen' region is determined by the location of the partners, whose accumulated expertise, existing collaborations and overlapping responsibilities in waste management provide a strong foundation for the alliance. Many of the partners have a long history of cooperation and have already implemented numerous successful projects, facilitated by excellent infrastructure connections that enable effective cooperation. The existing cross-border links (Dresden/Prague, etc.) already demonstrate the unique opportunities that cross-border constellations offer for the future. More than 40 partners involved in the conceptual phase and more than 80 identified and contacted supporters are based in the "Elbtal Sachsen" region. They want to seize the opportunity of a circular economy and resource management for fiber composites and contribute to the sustainability of the alliance during the implementation phase. In addition, there are five external partners and supporters whose expertise and technologies are important for immediate implementation and addressing regional issues.

Material cycle of fiber-reinforced composites

The technical and scientific state of the different phases in the life cycle of fiber composite materials varies (Figure 2). The manufacturing phase is characterized by a high level of maturity, including the production of fibers from various base materials (such as basalt, carbon, glass, etc.), the manufacturing of fibers with different morphological structures (AR-glass, pitch and PAN fibers, etc.), the production of semi-finished products with organic and inorganic surface coatings (epoxy resin, styrene-butadiene rubber, thermoplastics, etc.) and the manufacturing of semi-finished products and fiber composite materials with various structures and forms (woven fabrics, nonwovens, etc.) (Teschner, 2019). Research and development efforts include topics related to sustainable fiber production (such as carbon fibers from lignin and algae-based sources) (Arnold et al., 2018), the development of fire-resistant coatings, and the manufacturing of fiber composite materials from recycled fiber materials.

Figure 2: Material cycle of fiber-reinforced composites; © C³ Association

The use phase provides areas of application for composite fiber materials and determines both the material requirements and the desired properties of the materials. The material properties of these used composite materials depend on the production processes in the manufacturing phase. The processing phase follows the use phase and depends on the quality of the previously used materials. Therefore, research and development should focus on linking the manufacturing phase with the processing phase and developing materials and products for the utilisation phase based on this link. The state of the art for fiber composite materials in the processing phase is still limited and is essentially based on the state of the art for the recycling of conventional materials such as plastics, wood and mineral components. However, the state of scientific knowledge has advanced significantly in many areas, as demonstrated by the documented dismantling and demolition of structures made of composite fiber materials, the successful collection and sorting of composite fiber materials in the construction industry (camera-based sorting, etc.), and the processing of composite fiber materials (pyrolysis, solvolysis, blending with thermoplastic fibers, etc.) for reuse in the manufacture of new semi-finished products and products (production of yarns from rCF fibers, etc.) (Kortmann, 2020).

Basic projects

To implement the planned projects, two foundational projects were developed in collaboration with various alliance partners. Foundational Project B1 focuses on establishing an initial process chain for the production of semi-finished tools from recycled carbon fibers. Foundational Project B2 aims to assess the quality of fiber-containing waste and investigate how recycled fibers can be integrated into existing processes of companies in the region. Both foundational projects started at the end of 2022 or the beginning of 2023, with a duration of 14 months. The purpose of these foundational projects is to identify existing process chains and address any issues that may arise, providing proposed solutions. Based on the foundational projects, several follow-up projects are planned to address the identified questions and challenges.

RECYCLING

The recycling of fiber composites can be divided into different phases. In the following, the phases of recycling for carbon fibers, used in carbon fiber reinforced concrete (carbon concrete) are presented. The recycling of carbon concrete will be the first process chain, which shall be translated into

common practice in the Elbtal region by the WIR research alliance. The technology readiness level is very advanced in most of the recycling phases already. Apart from the continuous development and the optimization of the individual technologies, the translation of the available research results into the regional economy depicts the major challenge.

RECYCLING OF CARBON CONCRETE

In 2018, the demand for carbon fiber-reinforced plastics in the construction industry was 7,740 tons. With a growth rate of 12% per year, it can be anticipated that carbon fibers will increasingly be present in demolition waste from buildings in the long term. Therefore, recycling of this demolition material is essential. Recycling also involves the separation of the concrete matrix from the carbon fibers. As part of a research project, an initial assessment of the concrete and carbon reinforcement separation was conducted. A demonstrator building (Figure 3), constructed using carbon concrete, was demolished using standard equipment in the demolition process. The resulting fragments were subjected to crushing and processing. By reducing the fragments to a maximum particle size of 56 mm, the carbon reinforcement was completely separated from the concrete. It was not possible to confirm the presence of a significant amount of carbon remaining in the concrete. Through the utilization of various sorting devices (such as magnetic separation and camera-based single grain sorting), a separation efficiency greater than 99% was achieved. (Jan Kortmann, 2020).

Figure 3: Demonstrator building made out of carbon reinforced concrete; © Jan Kortmann, Florian Kopf

RECYCLING OF CARBON FIBERS

Carbon fibers used in concrete constructions are usually consisting of two components, the carbon fiber itself and a synthetic matrix, coating the fiber to ensure the adherence between the reinforcement and the concrete. In order to further process the the carbon fibers, they have to be separated from the synthetic matrix. The recycling of carbon fibers significant research challenges. Specifically, the successful separation of individual carbon fibers from the matrix, without causing damage to the fibers themselves, requires specialized knowledge. According to (Zhang et al., 2020), carbon fiber recycling can be categorized into three primary groups. The first approach is mechanical processing, which involves mechanically breaking down end-of-life components into their constituent parts. The second approach is thermal recycling, where high temperatures are employed to separate the carbon matrix from the fibers. The third approach is solvolysis, which entails extracting the matrix from the carbon fibers using a chemical solvent (Zhang et al., 2020). Figure 4 provides a concise overview of these procedures.

Figure 4: Recycling methods of carbon fibers, according to (Zhang et al., 2020)

REUSE OF RECYCLED CARBON FIBERS IN CARBON CONCRETE

In order to reuse recycled carbon fibers in carbon concrete, the carbon fibers need to be processed into semi-finished products by putting them into the desired shape and adding a synthetic matrix to them. Semi-finished products can take the form of rebars/rods or grids/fabrics, for example (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Left: Rebars made out of virgin carbon fibers, © Sven Hofmann; Right: Grids made out of virgin carbon fibers, © Stefan Groeschel

The basis for new rods and fabrics usually are continuous fibers. However, due to the recycling process, the recycled carbon fibers are only available in the form of short fibers in different lengths (depending on the recycling technologies used). To produce rods and fabrics, these short fibers need to be processed into yarn. For the production of yarn from recycled carbon fibers (rCF), a nonwoven fabric is first created through the carding process. This nonwoven fabric can be produced using either the dry-laid method or the wet-laid method (Xing et al., 2021). Both methods will be briefly explained here. Following the carding process, the nonwoven fabric is stretched and then spun into yarn. Figure 6 illustrates the simplified process chain for the production of staple fiber yarns.

Figure 6: Process chain for the production of fiber yarn

Fleece process

In order to transform individual short carbon fibers (Figure 8) into yarns, various methods can be employed, including the production of nonwovens. According to (Albrecht, 2000), the production of nonwovens can generally be categorized into dry processes, wet processes, and extrusion processes.

The selection of specific processes depends on the starting materials used. In the case of producing yarns from recycled fibers, the dry or wet processes are most suitable, as they both utilize short fibers as the initial material. The extrusion process, which involves using granulate as a base material, is not discussed in this article (Albrecht, 2000). Figure 7 provides a systematic representation of the wet and dry fleece processes.

Figure 7: Illustration of the wet and dry fleece process, according to (Albrecht, 2000)

Dry fleece process

The production of dry nonwoven fabrics involves the utilization of carding. This process results in the creation of fiber flocks or single-fiber fabrics. A carding machine consists of essential components such as a main drum with a cover or a main drum with worker and reversing rolls. The primary function of a carding machine is to organize the randomly presented mass of single fibers into a structured and desired fiber layer. Additionally, the carding machine must effectively present the fiber flock in terms of length and width over a specific unit of time. Moreover, the carding process helps in the cleaning of fibers and separation of foreign particles (Albrecht, 2000). The primary roller is responsible for processing the fibers into a fleece. To form a nonwoven fabric, the individual fiber fleeces are layered on top of each other. Further details regarding the specific formations of nonwovens can be found in reference (Albrecht, 2000).

Wet fleece process

The wetlaid process offers the advantage of being able to deposit all fibers that are dispersible in liquids into a nonwoven fabric. This process is characterized by excellent product homogeneity and high production efficiency. The basic production of wetlaid fabrics involves three steps. In the first step, the fibers are dispersed in water. The nonwoven fabric is then continuously formed by applying the dispersed fibers onto a screen belt. Simultaneously, water is filtered out through the screen belt during the nonwoven formation. In the second step, the nonwoven fabric is dried and rolled up for further processing (Albrecht, 2000). Finally, the individual tapes or nonwovens are combined into a continuous web using nozzles or funnels, and then stored (Hengstermann, Martin Cherif, Ch. & Weide, 2021).

Figure 8: Recycled carbon fibers

Staple yarn production

The produced fiber nonwoven is fed to a stretching process into a stretched web. Several creel webs are combined and stretched into a stretched web. The essential task of the stretching process is to align the fibers in the longitudinal direction. Besides, the fluctuations in the diameter of the individual webs are compensated by combining several webs (doubling). By using different feed speeds of the stretched webs, thick and thin spots in the web can be compensated. Another advantage of the stretching process is that the fibers are mixed and the individual webs are dusted (Hengstermann, Martin Cherif, Ch. & Weide, 2021). After the stretching process, the final spinning process takes place. In this process, the stretched tape is solidified and stretched to the final yarn fineness using various spinning processes (similar to cotton yarn production). The solidification of the yarn is achieved by twisting the fiber tape. Another dust removal of the fiber tape also takes place (Hengstermann, Martin Cherif, Ch. & Weide, 2021).

Rebar/rods production

Bars for carbon concrete are produced using the pultrusion process. In this process, a specific number of fibers are brought together according to the required reinforcement cross-section and impregnated with a plastic matrix. The subsequent pultrusion tool, which defines the geometry, is used to create the desired shape of the bar. Finally, the continuous fiber-matrix strand is fully cured through a temperature treatment. Depending on the type of impregnation, the bars may be susceptible to deformation at a later stage. With thermoplastic impregnation, the bars can be reshaped through the application of heat. However, once epoxy resin, for example, has cured, subsequent deformation is no longer possible (Curbach, 2019).

Grid production

The production of nonwoven fabrics (grids/mats) from recycled fibers can be achieved through three different methods:

1. Mat formation using pre-fabricated rods
2. Mat formation using textile surface formation processes
3. Mat formation using direct yarn placement

Mat formation using pre-fabricated rods

The production of nonwoven fabrics using pre-fabricated rods is similar to mat formation in reinforced concrete construction. In this method, individual rods with relatively large cross-sections are placed in large spacing distances, usually in two layers, in a crossing pattern. The rods are connected to each other at the intersections, either by adhesive bonding or through non-metallic clamping or binding connections. This approach differs from traditional steel mesh reinforcement, where the rods are typically welded at the intersections (Curbach, 2019).

Mat formation using textile surface formation processes

For the production of mats using textile surface formation processes, the knowledge and techniques of the textile industry are utilized. The yarns are interconnected through methods such as weaving or warp knitting. In the warp knitting process, multiple parallel, unimpregnated yarns are laid down in both the transverse and longitudinal directions (warp and weft directions) relative to the production direction. At the intersections of the warp and weft threads, they are sewn or intertwined using a stitch thread. Subsequently, the mat can be subjected to impregnation. Similar to rod production, different types of plastics can be used for impregnation in this process as well (Curbach, 2019).

Mat formation using direct yarn placement

In the production of mats using direct yarn placement, an unimpregnated yarn is directly soaked and laid down using a tension frame, portal robot, as well as drying and curing units. Since the yarns are glued directly onto each other, a separate connection at the intersections is not necessary. One significant advantage of direct yarn placement is the ability to adjust the yarn placement according to the required reinforcement level. In less stressed areas, the yarn can be placed with larger distances between them. In more heavily stressed areas, the yarn spacing is reduced. Once the laying process is complete, the mats can be subjected to drying (Curbach, 2019).

CONCLUSION

The information contained in this article aims to provide an initial overview of carbon fiber recycling. By establishing a regional alliance in Saxony and involving a variety of research institutions and companies, the recycling of carbon fiber from, for example, end-of-life components, will be investigated on an industrial scale. Through constructive networking of existing knowledge and the application of technological processes, the carbon cycle is intended to be closed in the coming years. The fundamental processes of recycling methods and the re-manufacturing of semi-finished tools are also explained in this article. By independently setting goals within the WIR alliance and implementing foundational initiatives and subsequent projects, a contribution to the reduction of CO₂ emissions and waste avoidance is thus intended to be achieved.

The process steps mentioned in this article are established procedures for recycling carbon fibers. First yarns and rods made from recycled carbon fibers have already been produced and investigated. A continuous development and improvement of the carbon rods is taking place through ongoing exchange among all partners of the alliance.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

No data was assembled for the production of this paper.

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.